

MASTERS THESIS

Pellet Modelling: HPI2 upgrade and validation in tokamak WEST

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Foreword

The Institut de Recherche sur la Fusion par confinement Magnétique (IRFM) at the Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique (CEA) is at the forefront of research in the field of nuclear fusion. As part of my master's thesis, I had the privilege of joining IRFM and immersing myself in a dynamic environment where cutting-edge fusion technologies are developed and studied. This report aims to provide insights into my enriching experience during my internship at IRFM, specifically focusing on the challenges I encountered and the contributions I made to the pellet modelling project.

One of the central aspects of my internship was delving into the world of pellet modelling, particularly focusing on the HPI2 code. Developed in Matlab, a language I had limited familiarity with before commencing my internship, HPI2 posed a formidable challenge. Collaborating with Florian Koechl and Bernard Pégourié, I undertook the intricate task of understanding and modifying the code to suit the evolving requirements of our pellet injection research. The journey was accompanied by its share of complexities, partly due to the limited documentation and structure of the HPI2 code.

Amidst these challenges, I seized the opportunity to enhance my programming skills and gain a deeper understanding of fusion physics. I engaged in a rigorous process of self-appropriation of the source code, piecing together its functionalities, and gradually incorporating modifications to improve its reliability and performance. This process underscored the significance of perseverance, collaborative problem-solving, and adaptability in tackling computational challenges.

The resumption of pellet injection modelling efforts at the WEST facility presented a unique set of hurdles. The scarcity of relevant data and the presence of bugs within the HPI2 code further intensified the complexity of the project. However, these obstacles served as opportunities for growth. By collaborating with experts at IRFM and meticulously examining the code, I identified and resolved critical issues, contributing to the debugging and refinement of the HPI2 code. This achievement marked a significant step forward, transforming the code into a dependable tool that can now be seamlessly integrated into routine fusion research operations.

In conclusion, my time at IRFM was a journey of technical and personal development. The challenges I faced while navigating the HPI2 code and grappling with data availability issues have not only enriched my understanding of fusion research but have also honed my problem-solving skills. Through this report, I aim to document my experiences and contributions, shedding light on the intricate world of pellet modelling and its pivotal role in advancing the field of nuclear fusion.

Contents

1	Introduction	6
1.1	Nuclear Fusion	6
1.2	Magnetic Confinement and Tokamak	7
1.3	Tokamak WEST	10
2	Pellet Fuelling	12
2.1	Injection	12
2.2	Ablation	13
2.3	Homogenization	14
3	HPI2 Model	17
3.1	HPI2 Model Upgrade	19
3.2	Study in striation frequency	20
3.3	Drift stop analysis: rational surfaces	21
4	HPI2 Model Validation in WEST Tokamak	25
4.1	Validation method	25
4.1.1	Uncertainty in validation	26
4.2	Results	27
4.2.1	One plasma	27
4.2.2	Multiple cases	32
4.3	Discussion	33
5	Conclusion and Future Outlook	37
A	Appendix: Additional figures	41

1 Introduction

Although during this study we have focused on modelling the fueling of the tokamak reactor, we will start with a brief introduction of the main ideas and the state-of-the-art of nuclear fusion research.

1.1 Nuclear Fusion

The dream of nuclear fusion as a source of energy is inspired by the nuclear fusion reactions that heats the stars, where vast amounts of energy are released by merging hydrogen nuclei and forming heavier nuclei, such as helium. This process has the potential to provide a constant and virtually limitless source of clean energy, with minimal environmental impact compared to fossil fuels. However, achieving nuclear fusion on Earth is a complex endeavor that requires the collaboration of various scientific and technological disciplines. While significant progress has been made, there are still challenges to overcome. The development of nuclear fusion could have a transformative impact on our lives, addressing the pressing need for sustainable and reliable energy sources, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and mitigating climate change effects.

The principle of fusion energy involves merging two lighter nuclei into a heavier one, releasing energy in the process. Currently, the most promising reaction is the fusion of deuterium and tritium into helium, releasing a neutron and energy in the process. There are several benefits to this choice, but the most relevant one is the relatively high reaction cross-section at relatively low temperatures compared to other reactions. Deuterium exists in seawater in sufficient quantities to meet our energy needs in the foreseeable future. However, tritium is very scarce in nature as it is a radioactive isotope that decays. Due to this, one of the requirements for fusion as a future energy source is to find an efficient way to produce tritium. The most important proposed method for this is carried out through the "breeding" of tritium in a blanket region around the reactor. This blanket region would allow the neutrons produced in the fusion reaction to interact with lithium, fissioning it and thus creating tritium self-sufficiently. This blanket is called the "tritium breeding blanket" and will be an essential part of future fusion reactors.

Achieving fusion is not an easy task as atomic nuclei are positively charged, generating a repulsive force between them. The two nuclei need very high speeds to overcome this force, with the help of tunnel effect, the required energy is called the Coulomb barrier. One way to achieve this is through thermonuclear fusion, which involves heating a group of nuclei until their thermal speeds are high enough to overcome the Coulomb barrier. This requires extremely high temperatures, on the order of 100 million Kelvin. Currently, in many fusion research facilities, the particles exist in the form of plasma that needs to be confined. Confinement is important for many reasons. One reason is to keep the plasma in a small volume so that the density and pressure remain high. Another reason is to protect any wall material from the extreme temperatures of the plasma and likewise protect the plasma from interacting with any wall material, which would cause it to cool down and become contaminated.

Before moving on, we would like to introduce the state-of-the-art of the nuclear fusion research, led by ITER organization. ITER is an esteemed international nuclear fusion research initiative located in France, with the primary objective of verifying the practicability of nuclear fusion as a sustainable and environmentally benign energy source. Central to the evaluation of fusion reactor efficacy is the Q factor, commonly referred to as the fusion gain. The Q factor denotes the ratio of energy produced from fusion reactions to the energy input necessary for plasma sustenance and heating. With a targeted Q factor of 10, ITER endeavors to demonstrate the capacity to generate tenfold more energy from fusion reactions than is expended to uphold the plasma state, thereby substantiating the viability of fusion as a promising and viable energy solution. Consequently ITER is planned to have dominant alpha particle heating (coming from the fusion reaction) in the plasma, unlike previous experiments (as JET), so the physics can be quite different. This is part of the obstacles that ITER should overcome.

Figure 1: Schematic image of a Tokamak. Source: ITER <https://www.iter.org/newsline/-/3037>

1.2 Magnetic Confinement and Tokamak

Since a plasma is a collection of charged particles, it can be confined by a magnetic field. Using the equation $\vec{F} = q\vec{E} + q\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$, we obtain the Lorentz force \vec{F} experienced by a particle with charge q and velocity \vec{v} in an electric and magnetic field \vec{E} and \vec{B} , respectively. This force allows charged particles to move freely along the magnetic field lines. However, if they try to move perpendicular to the magnetic field lines, a force is exerted that changes the direction of the particle's trajectory.

Assuming the absence of an electric field, the force exerted is always perpendicular to the particle's trajectory, so no energy is added to the particle. If we also assume a uniform magnetic field, the magnitude of the force is constant and can be equated to a centripetal force that forces the particle to follow the magnetic field lines in a helical trajectory since it cannot move freely in the plane perpendicular to the magnetic field lines. This basically limits the particle to move on a cylindrical surface whose radius is determined by the strength of the magnetic field, the mass of the particle, and the component of velocity perpendicular to the field lines.

The tokamak is the most relevant fusion reactor type nowadays, it is a torus where the plasma is magnetically confined. In a tokamak, the magnetic field lines are curved, forming a torus shape. This causes charged particles to follow a curved path. This is shown in Figure 1, where the toroidal magnetic field is created by toroidal coils. Previously, we assumed that the magnetic field was uniform and that there was no electric field. However, since the field lines curve along the torus, the magnetic field is no longer uniform. As a result, the magnetic field becomes slightly stronger in the innermost region of the torus compared to the outer region, which is referred to as the High Field Side (HFS) and Low Field Side (LFS) respectively. This gradient in magnetic field intensity causes the charged particle orbiting along the torus to deviate based on its electric charge. This leads to a separation of charges, creating an electric field that results in plasma confinement loss. One way to address this problem is by connecting the upper and lower parts of the plasma, effectively adding a current to the plasma. This induces a poloidal magnetic field (both represented by green arrows in Figure 1). The plasma current is usually initiated by an internal solenoid, also depicted in the figure. The addition of the poloidal magnetic field results in a helical magnetic field that adequately compensates for the previously mentioned deviations, thereby achieving proper plasma confinement.

Due to the toroidal geometry of the tokamak and its symmetries, the plasma is described using toroidal coordinates, as shown in Figure 2. Thus, any point within the plasma can be described by the toroidal angle Φ , the poloidal angle θ , and the minor radius r . However, the radial coordinate can be described

Figure 2: Toroidal coordinates. Source: CIEMAT. http://fusionwiki.ciemat.es/wiki/Toroidal_coordinates

by a different quantity that guarantees certain symmetries in the poloidal angle.

In a tokamak plasma, there are magnetic flux surfaces where certain quantities are conserved. These magnetic flux surfaces are closed surfaces in the plasma where the dot product of the magnetic field and the surface normal is zero at all points. In a tokamak, these surfaces are nested torus. One way to refer to these surfaces is through the magnetic flux passing through them, from the magnetic axis (in the middle of the plasma) to the flux surface itself. This is called poloidal flux ψ . The flux surfaces provide a new way to describe the minor radial coordinate for a plasma, ensuring that certain quantities are constant in θ for a given ψ

If all magnetic flux surfaces were closed, impurities would accumulate inside the plasma, severely affecting its performance. Therefore, beyond a certain radial point, flux surfaces are generally open, creating a channel through which particles can leave the plasma. We refer to the Last Closed Flux Surface (LCFS) as the "Separatrix," which forms a characteristic point called the "X-point." All of this can be observed in Figure 3, which shows the poloidal section of the plasma with three flux surfaces: a closed one, the separatrix, and an open one. The open field line trajectory in the confined plasma leads to the divertor plates. These plates are designed to withstand the intense bombardment of particles at high temperatures compared to other components facing the plasma, such as the inner walls of the tokamak.

An important factor to consider in plasma performance is the impurities it contains. These are usually described by the effective charge of ions, defined in equation 1, where n_i is the density of ions with charge Z_i . In fusion plasmas, temperatures are generally high enough that most atoms are fully ionized¹. This implies that the electron density can be approximated as $n_e = \sum_k n_k Z_k$.

$$Z_{eff} = \frac{\sum_k n_k Z_k^2}{\sum_k n_k Z_k} = \frac{\sum_k n_k Z_k^2}{n_e} \quad (1)$$

Impurities in the plasma can come from different sources: fusion products themselves, the tokamak chamber wall, or intentionally introduced into the plasma. We can add some impurities to enhance the radiative power near the LCFS for modifying the heat and particles transport and to reduce power that goes to the divertor.

The shape of a tokamak plasma is often characterized by various parameters, where R and z refer to Figure 2. One of the most fundamental shape parameters is the major radius, given by equation 2, where R_{max} and R_{min} are the maximum and minimum values of R along the separatrix.

$$R_0 = (R_{max} + R_{min})/2 \quad (2)$$

¹However, in the case of heavy impurities as tungsten, which is generally used for plasma facing components, the atoms are rarely fully ionised.

Figure 3: Schematic view of the poloidal section of flux surfaces. Source: [1]

Another parameter is the minor radius of the tokamak, calculated using equation 3.

$$a = (R_{max} - R_{min})/2 \quad (3)$$

In addition to these two parameters, triangularity is also relevant due to its influence on plasma behavior. Triangularity can be divided into upper and lower triangularity, where upper triangularity is given by Equation 4, with $R_{z_{max}}$ being the value of R at the highest z along the separatrix.

$$\delta_u = \frac{R_0 - R_{z_{max}}}{a} \quad (4)$$

Lower triangularity δ_l is defined in the same way, but using the value of R at the lowest z along the separatrix instead. The total triangularity of a plasma is therefore the average of the upper and lower triangularity. Another relevant quantity for the plasma shape is the elongation κ defined as:

$$\kappa = \frac{z_{max} - z_{min}}{R_{max} - R_{min}}. \quad (5)$$

An important parameter in evaluating the performance of a tokamak is the energy confinement time τ_E . The energy confinement time is a measure of how long it takes for a plasma to release energy to its surroundings. As such, it is a direct measure of the confinement properties of the device. If the energy confinement time is doubled, it implies that the configuration is twice as good at confining plasma energy.

The safety factor (q) in a tokamak is a crucial parameter that measures the stability of the plasma confinement. It is defined as in equation 6, where B_t and B_p are the toroidal and poloidal components of the magnetic field, respectively.

$$q = \frac{rB_t}{RB_p} \quad (6)$$

Intuitively is the ratio of the times a particular magnetic field line travels around a toroidal confinement area's "long way" (toroidally) to the "short way" (poloidally). The safety factor influences the plasma's stability and is vital for preventing disruptions and instabilities during fusion reactions. Maintaining an optimal safety factor is essential for the successful operation of a tokamak fusion device.

1.3 Tokamak WEST

Due to the fact that this work has been conducted in the *Institut de Recherche sur la Fusion par confinement Magnétique* (IRFM), some of the parts in it are focused on the tokamak WEST, located in the institute, so we will introduce it.

The Cadarache research facility in France is home to the experimental fusion device known as WEST (Tungsten (W) Environment in Steady-state Tokamak). WEST tokamak serves as a valuable testing ground for various components and technologies that will be used in ITER. In fact, the WEST tokamak's main objective is to investigate and confirm the usage of tungsten as a plasma-facing material in a fusion reactor. Due to its high melting point and effective heat-handling properties, tungsten is a strong contender for this position since it can withstand the harsh conditions found within a fusion reactor.

The WEST tokamak is equipped with advanced plasma heating and diagnostic systems to investigate

Figure 4: Picture of the inside of the toroidal chamber of WEST tokamak. Source: IRFM.

various operational scenarios and plasma confinement techniques. Its research primarily focuses on achieving and sustaining long-pulse, high-performance plasmas in a steady-state operation, which is a crucial requirement for the practical implementation of fusion energy.

The shape of the tokamak is defined by a minor radius of 0.5 m, a major radius of 2.5 m and a plasma volume of 15 m^3 . Some engineering parameters are a plasma current around 1 MA, a toroidal field of 3.7 T at the core, an ICRH (Ion Cyclotron Resonant Heating) heating power of 9 MW, and a LHCD (Low Hybrid Current Drive) heating power of 7 MW. Some components of the tokamak (such as the divertor) are made of tungsten, as tungsten tests are one of the main scopes of the device. In the figures 5(a) and 5(b) we can see an example of the magnetic configuration of WEST tokamak, in the left the flux surfaces show the magnetic equilibrium, pointing out the last closed flux surface. In the right, a typical safety factor q profile for WEST is shown. To follow a detailed analysis in WEST tokamak we refer to [2], [3] and [4].

Several european fusion research facilities collaborate in a association known as EuroFUSION where

Figure 5: Example of the magnetic configuration of WEST. **(a)** Poloidal cut showing magnetic equilibrium. Red closed line shows the LCFS. Black contour line show the elements closest to the plasma in the tokamak chamber. **(b)** Safety factor profile in terms of the normalized minor radius.

fusion technology is promoted, and WEST is one of the major instruments supporting their research efforts in the several fusion research projects they are participating in. The collaboration in the area of nuclear fusion research is a key factor connecting WEST, ITER, and EuroFUSION. These partnerships support ITER in its goal to establish continuous nuclear fusion and pave the path for later fusion power plants, helping to further the development of fusion technology.

The most interesting WEST feature for this study is the pellet injector that, jointly with the gas injection is capable of fueling the plasma to sustain it.

2 Pellet Fuelling

The topic in which this work is primarily focused on is the modelling of the pellet fuelling, mainly in tokamaks. This kind of fuelling is based on the injection of cryogenized projectiles inside the plasma. These pellets are composed of fuelling material such as deuterium or hydrogen in order to sustain or increase the plasma density, so the plasma can reach appropriate conditions for the fusion reaction.

Although particle fuelling in modern tokamaks is primarily accomplished by neutral gas puffing from the plasma periphery and by neutral beam injection (NBI, always very marginal and hard to use because it couples matter and energy injection), due to increased neutral opacity and a modest particle source from the NBI, gas fueling may become ineffective in future reactors. The injection of cryogenic pellets [5], which have greater penetration and quicker response times, is a practical substitute as a major fueling approach. To optimize the particle source and provide fueling in the plasma core, where the pellet is ablated, the pellet mass, injection speed, and frequency can be concurrently modified. To maintain the density necessary for a $Q = 10$ baseline ELMy H-mode scenario at 15 MA in ITER, for instance, pellets with mass between 2 and $5.5 \cdot 10^{21}$ atoms and frequency between 1.5 and 3.5 Hz should be sufficient.[6] To appreciate a real example of pellet fuelling, we refer to the Appendix A, in the figure 32 we can see the change in number of electrons inside the tokamak after the three pellet injections during the plasma shot.

2.1 Injection

Although the injection and the injector itself is not the main part of this project, it is relevant to mention it as it will be one of the biggest source of uncertainties in the experimental results, due to the nature of the process. We will describe the WEST injection system as stated in [7].

The Pellet Injection system, in figure 6 enables the injection of pellets ranging in size from 2 mm^3 to 8 mm^3 through 4 tracks that may be switched during a pulse in under 100 ms. The injection can be done from the Low Field Side (LFS) or from the High Field Side (HFS), the former has been reported to be less efficient in terms of particles going inside the Last Close Flux Surface (LCFS), due to the ∇B drift (explained in detail in section 2.3), for the same reason the latter is more efficient in this way, but this HFS injection has to be performed using curved pipes that can erode and decrease the velocity of the pellet. HFS injection takes place on three tracks (upper, middle and lower), while LFS injection occurs only on one track, as it can be appreciated in the figure 7). The continuous screw extruder used in the pellet injector created by PELIN Laboratory (Russia) is suitable for producing H_2 or D_2 ice over lengthy periods of time (up to 2000s, or 100 m of D_2 ice or 20,000 pellets). [8]. The width (pellet length) of the rectangular-shaped ice rod at the screw's output may be changed shot per shot between 0.7 and 2.5 mm. A first camera that can inspect the ice condition keeps an eye on it. A 2 mm diameter punch with a trigger frequency up to 10 Hz cuts pellets in the rod. Each pellet in the gun barrel is accelerated by a brief burst of high pressure gas that is propelled by a quick electromagnetic valve. For slower speeds (less than 200 m/s), up to 5 bar of helium gas and 100 bar of hydrogen are employed as propellant, respectively. The pellets are delivered to the selection box, which chooses the injection track, through a straight guide tube with a low conductivity for the gas. Two pumped gas expansion volumes reduce the amount of propellant gas that would otherwise reach the plasma. Finally, a second camera activated by optical barriers performs the pellet diagnostic by photographing the integrity of the pellets and estimating their volume and velocity (figure 6). Depending on pellet length, the pellet injector system's injection capacity ranges from 7 to $11 \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, or $2 - 3 \cdot 10^{20}$ atoms per pellet, injected at up to 10 Hz with a 95% reliability.

Unfortunately for our study, the diagnostics that measures the mass and the velocity of the pellet entering the toroidal chamber are not working currently, so this increase somehow the uncertainty in the modelling results. We will comment more about this issue in the section 4.

Figure 6: Pellet injector and diagnostics in WEST tokamak. Source: [7]

2.2 Ablation

Just after being introduced in the tokamak plasma, pellets start a process called ablation. As the pellet approach the plasma, particles starts to hit it and ablate the material from the solid pellet to the plasma. In the edge of the plasma the density is lower so less particles reach the pellet, then the ablation rate is proportional to heat flux. First the pellet is alone, completely naked, but as plasma particles collide they extract neutrals from the pellet surface (and lose energy too), that form a neutral cloud. This will be the first barrier against the plasma that the pellet will develop (similar to the Leidenfrost effect in liquids). Then, as the particle flux is higher, the density of the neutral cloud is also higher. After particles keep colliding with neutral cloud, they ionise the outer parts, that form an ionised cloud. This new cloud is affected by the magnetic field (guiding center of ions and electrons following magnetic field lines). Then the trajectory of this ionised cloud would separate it from the pellet and the neutral cloud. This neutral cloud is being constantly generated (ablation of pellet) and ionised (by plasma particles), reaching an stationary state. Note that the particles that can reach the pellet surface are mainly electrons, due to the fact that ions will have a much larger cross section so they will be stopped before reaching the pellet surface. Even the electrons get to the pellet with an energy $E \sim 0$ (much lower compared with the plasma electrons), because the ice sublimation energy is extremely low.

Therefore, we find several kinds of pellet shielding. The most efficient one is the Coulomb stopping, where the heat flux is absorbed by collisions as we have just described. Another less efficient pellet shielding is caused by the electrostatic sheath formed in the plasma cloud interface, principally repelling electrons. Finally the least efficient shielding would be the cloud diamagnetism, which reduces the effective area of the plasma flux tube intercepted by the cloud (local disorption of magnetic field lines). We can illustrate this process with the simplistic representation in figure 8.

Additionally, when using LH heating, the fast electrons affected by the LH wave, which are denominated as suprathermal electrons, also have some effect in the ablation that should be taking into account when launching pellets while using this heating system. In the WEST tokamak LH heating presents a limitation in the use of pellets, as the ablation could happen sooner than desired, meaning less penetration.

While the ablation process is happening, the ion cloud or "plasmoid" will follow the magnetic field lines

Figure 7: Representative figure of the 4 injection paths that pellets can follow before entering in the tokamak chamber.

and go through the homogenization process, so the pellet will increase the electron and ion density of the background plasma, which is the scope of pellet injection. In the subsection 2.3 the homogenization process will be detailed.

2.3 Homogenization

When the pellet is ablated, it is leaving this ionised clouds along its path, this is because this plasmoids are affected by the magnetic field while the pellet and neutral cloud are not, so the pellet and neutral cloud go out of the plasmoid. We can find an illustrative representation in the figure 31 in the Appendix A. These plasmoids are generally a thousand times denser and colder than the background plasma. The homogenization is produced along the field lines in both directions, however, the parallel energy transport

Figure 8: Simplified scheme showing the process of ablation and the formation of clouds around the pellet in a magnetic field. Source: Bernard Pegourie.

Figure 9: Simplified scheme explaining ∇B drift in tokamaks. Source: Bernard Pegourie.

Figure 10: Scheme showing the magnetic tension drift stopping mechanism. Source: Bernard Pegourie.

is much faster (thermal electron velocity) than the parallel density transport (at sound velocity), so temperatures in cloud and background plasma equilibrates much faster than the densities. Due to this phenomenon we have an over-pressured plasmoid. Derived from this effect, the plasmoid will suffer a charge separation due to the vertical drift of electrons and ions, $v_{\nabla B_{e,i}}$ caused by the gradient of the magnetic field B_∞ (background magnetic field in the absence of the pellet $B_\infty \approx B_t$). This charge separation induce a current $\delta j_{\nabla B}$ which is compensated by a polarization current j_{pol} , driven by an electric field E . This electric field induces a $E \times B_\infty$ drift in the Low Field Side (LFS) direction, i.e. outwards from the torus center, which correspond with the direction of the gradient of the magnetic field. We can see this process on the figure 9.

The acceleration caused by this drift can be described with the expression (complete discussion in [9]):

$$\left[\frac{dV_d}{dt} \right]_{\nabla B} = \frac{2(n_0 T_0 (1 + M_0^2/2) - n_\infty T_\infty)}{R_c n_0 m_0} \quad (7)$$

T_∞ and n_∞ stand for the background plasma temperature and density, respectively. T_0 , M_0 , and m_0 represent the temperature, Mach number, and ion mass of the parallel expansion of the plasmoid. Finally R_c is the curvature radius of magnetic field lines (can be approximated to major radius).

When a cloud starts to drift during the first stage of ideal magnetohydrodynamics (MHD), it drags away the magnetic flux tube it encounters. An Alfvén wave moving at the Alfvén velocity (C_A) propels the potential distribution along the flux tube. This process is seen in Figure 10, where the magnetic tension produces a counterforce that slows the drift by exerting a force per unit surface $F_m = B_\infty^2/2\mu_0$ that operates in the direction of the cloud's displacement. Where μ_0 is the magnetic permittivity in the vacuum.

As time passes, the cloud's electric potential disturbance extends across the entire magnetic surface, and its length normally grows at the speed of sound $C_s(T_0)$. This growth is significant enough to include sizable angular sections of poloidal and toroidal shapes. This induces the two methods that dampen the cloud drift more effectively than the Alfvén damping does.

Figure 11: Scheme showing the drift stopping mechanisms: external connection **(a)** and internal connection **(b)**. Source: Bernard Pegourie.

When two regions with opposing charges are connected by a single flux tube, a process known as External Connection (EC) occurs, as illustrated in Figure 11(a). Along this flux tube, a resistive parallel current j_{\parallel} circulates, originating from the cloud itself. The dampening effect caused by Alfvén wave emission gradually diminishes within this regime. Here, the parallel conductivity of the plasma and the length of the flux tube that links the two ends of the cloud contribute as inputs to the equation describing the drift velocity’s evolution. The presence of integer rational surfaces in the safety factor significantly hinders the drift, leading to its reduction near these surfaces. This effect arises from the decrease in charge separation. When the "connection line" between the negative and positive regions suddenly shortens, the connection becomes more effective, causing the drift to cease more rapidly. This can be seen in the figure 11(a), where with $q \approx 2$ by definition of the safety factor the magnetic lines connecting both regions are forced to make 2 turns over the toroidal chamber, the number of turns is bigger when q is not integer and not half integer. In studies such as [10] the role of the rational surfaces has been carefully studied in the homogenization of pellets.

The second process, known as Internal Connection (IC), develops as a result of the current $\delta j_{\nabla B}$ gradual misalignment as its parallel length steadily lengthens and expands to encompass larger poloidal and toroidal angular sectors. Beyond a critical length, the relative directions of the current $\delta j_{\nabla B}$ with respect to the field lines reverse at the two extremities of the cloud. As a result, as seen in Figure 11(b), a parallel current develops inside the cloud. Despite not directly braking the drift, this phenomena considerably lessens its driving force.

Due to the influence of these two mechanisms, the kinetics of the drift and the consequent matter deposition profile are dependent on the particular magnetic configuration of the device (tokamak, stellarator, or RFP). MHD simulations, as discussed in [11], offer more details on this subject.

3 HPI2 Model

After introducing the pellet ablation and homogenization principle, we will introduce the model on which this study is based.

The HPI2 model stands for Hydrogen Pellet Injection, and effectively models the fuelling process of the pellets since the moment it enters inside the toroidal chamber (in tokamak or stellarator) with a certain velocity. As explained in the theory, it can be divided into two subparts: the ablation, where ablation rate is calculated taking into account plasma profiles and other aspects of the plasma, and the homogenization, where the ablated material homogenize with the plasma and increase the plasma density. This code was developed initially in Fortran [12] and translated to Matlab after [13].

During this work, one of the main aspects has been to understand how the HPI2 model perform its predictions and to know the main elements that compound it, apart from the debugging work that comes with any computational work.

The model calculates the pellet particle ablation rate based on a Neutral Gas and Plasma Shielding (NGPS) model [14], considering the influence of fast ions and electrons. A plasmoid drift acceleration balance equation is developed to explain the observations, considering fluid continuity, plasma drift relations, and the expansion of plasmoids. To brake the drift, as explained in section 2, the Alfvén wave-induced drift damping effect is introduced based on ideal magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) conditions, showing that resistive effects can be neglected if stronger damping mechanisms occur in the later phase of the drift process. External and internal parallel short-circuit currents are considered to explain further reduction in drift. An integrated plasmoid homogenization model is refined, which treats the influence of fast ions during the homogenization process, so the complete model, implemented in HPI2, solves a set of 29 coupled ordinary differential equations to determine the pellet particle deposition profile, accounting for plasmoid drift and arbitrary pellet injection configurations. Validation efforts of HPI2 show good overall agreement with experimentally measured drift displacement for selected pellet injection cases [13].

The timeline of the model calculation goes as follows: The equilibrium profiles are first read during code execution, then the entrance of the pellet is simulated, and the ablation is calculated. When T_∞ (referring to T_e) is below a predetermined threshold, the simple Neutral Gas Shielding (NGS) model is used to speed up computation, but once the temperature is high enough, we calculate the ablated plasmoids with the Neutral Gas and Plasma Shielding (NGPS) model, which is more complicated and calculates the plasmoid for each ablation (takes into account not only the pellet shielding of the neutral gas but also the plasmoid cloud). The code thus determines the plasmoid, the ablation rate, and finally the homogenization of the plasmoid in the plasma which takes into account all the effects derived from the ∇B drift that has been explained.

All this process is performed by the model discretizing the propagation of the pellet in the plasma by step of size dx . The code is performing this loop where the pellet position is advanced a step dx at each loop and then for each iteration the ablation and the homogenization are computed. So, each dx space step the process is repeated until the pellet is completely ablated and no more material is present.

The principal inputs for the model are then, the plasma equilibrium, T_e and n_e profiles, and also pellet characteristics such as mass, velocity, and injection direction. The final deposition profile, density, and temperature profile are then calculated, and this represents the main output of the model.

To have a more clear idea about the output of HPI2, we can observe some examples in the figures 12(a) and 12(b), where the plasmoid drift, ablation and deposition profiles have been calculated during the HPI2 process. Finally we will get the final electron density profile that can be compared with the initial one to measure the effect of the pellet in the plasma, we have this comparison in the figure 13. We observe that in some occasions the effect on the pellet can be quite notorious, although this is just an illustrative example.

Figure 12: Example of some HPI2 calculations. (a) Plasmoid drift calculated during the homogenization process. (b) Ablation (red) and deposition (blue) profiles after pellet injection.

Figure 13: Electron density profile before pellet injection (continuous line) and after pellet calculated by HPI2 model (dashed line).

3.1 HPI2 Model Upgrade

After we developed a good understanding of the code behind HPI2, we noticed that the space step dx for calculating each plasmoid was a constant parameter that the user establish before launching the simulation. So we research on the difference between different values of dx in terms of the calculated deposition profile. In this way we can see in figure 14 an example run in HPI2 in a LFS case, where the different profiles differ in an important factor for different values of dx , this difference is not negligible and it shouldn't be attached to an arbitrary parameter, as dx is for the HPI2 model. So we decide to give a more physical meaning to the distance in which we calculate the plasmoid. The reason behind is that due to the ∇B drift and the pellet velocity, after the formation of the plasmoid, this one drifts (and follow the magnetic field lines) and the pellet goes out of it, so another plasmoid forms. Then the election of the dx parameter is meaningful and should be attached to the distance in which those plasmoids forms. Also regarding the rational surfaces that the plasmoid could encounter, that are quite dependant on the position.

Figure 14: HPI2 deposition profiles of electron density in a LFS case, calculated varying the space step for the calculation of the plasmoids dx , and using the calculated variable dx . Input data corresponding to shot 55589 in WEST C4 campaign.

The physical approach would naturally be assign dx to the distance in which the pellet goes out of the plasmoid, this can be well approximated by $dx = t_{exit} \cdot v_{pellet}$, being v_{pellet} a constant parameter of the injection velocity and t_{exit} the time it takes for the pellet to go out of the plasmoid, which is a quantity calculated during the homogenization part² inside the HPI2 code, so for each plasmoid, this quantity is different and dx is no longer a constant value, but a variable. In the Appendix A we can find the figure 31 that illustrates the plasmoid ejection process and the variable t_{exit} itself.

Then, the change in dx would represent a more natural way to calculate the plasmoids in the HPI2 code, following a physical reasoning and not a unique and arbitrary dx without connection with the physics of the process. Then when the pellet goes out of the plasmoid, a new plasmoid is calculated. In general, we would expect that if we have a lower dx as resolution improves, then the quality of the results should improve, but the reality is that depending of this arbitrary dx , different rational surfaces could affect the process, so to obtain the most optimum results we must choose the physical way. In addition, choosing a dx value too low could affect to the calculation time of the model, which would be desirable to improve somehow. In fact, if the dx parameter is too low we could have some numerical convergence problems when calculating the ablation rate inside the code. In the figure 14 we can observe the difference in the

²The quantity t_{exit} represents the calculated time that the pellet, taking into account its velocity and the drift velocity of the plasmoid, takes to go out of the plasmoid. Among other plasmoids quantities, this one is calculated inside the sector of the code that calculates the homogenization process.

deposition profile taking dx as constant and calculating it physically for each plasmoid. We can see that the differences are not negligible, therefore the election of this change is meaningful for the results of the model and likely represents an improvement of it.

In addition, as stated, it would be desirable to decrease the computation time of the model. We know

Figure 15: HPI2 density profile using different values of the factor A , compared with the initial density profile.

that the higher the dx value, the faster is the code, as we calculate less plasmoids and the homogenization part is the most time consuming. So we would like to increase our variable dx in a factor that respects the ideology and the physics behind, but whose results variation is small enough to be considered reasonable. For this purpose we create the factor A that will multiply the variable dx , so $A = 1$ is the original one. We can see the difference in the deposition profile in the figure 15 for different values of A , where we can infer that the higher reasonable value for A would be $A = 2$, which reduce the computation time to almost one half but still produce good results compared with the original ones. We see also how bigger values for the A factor can affect too much the final output. In conclusion, the A values between 1 and 2 are proper to improve the time and decrease the resources used by the code without hurting the final results of HPI2. Bigger values of A will give undesired imprecision on the results.

3.2 Study in striation frequency

The ablation light emitted by Hydrogen pellets injected in fusion devices is strongly modulated. This is clearly seen on photographs where ablation clouds display a succession of bright and dark bands elongated along the magnetic field: the striations, which we can see in figure 16. This phenomenon is of particular importance since it can be associated with the quasi-periodic ejection of plasmoids, i.e. with the dx parameter discussed above. However, the frequency in which the plasmoids develops is not constant in the experiment and has a small part of randomness, this random behavior can affect the final profile of the electron density and could be mainly caused by the position of rational surfaces and the plasma equilibrium during the pellet injection. Then the position of the plasmoid ejection would be affecting the final result. To test this hypothesis we are going to use the factor A as the random part which should reflect the variation of the striation frequency, so we will follow the same procedure as before, but changing A as a random factor (uniform) between 0.5 and 2 in each plasmoid. In the figure 17 we can see the distribution of different deposition profiles of electronic density when running HPI2 with the factor A taking these random values for each calculation of the space step dx . We see that the variation between different runs is notably bigger in the deposition peaks (local maximum) and in the minimum, and also higher in the core than the edge, where the impact is lower as there is less ablation. It is worth noting that this HPI2 run has been done in a case where the pellet has been injected from

Figure 16: Picture of the ablation cloud of a pellet injected in Tore Supra, seen from the top of the vacuum chamber. R is the major radius and D_ϕ the distance in the toroidal direction. Source: [15].

the Low Field Side, other configurations could give us very different profiles with just one peak for example.

We can appreciate how the variation experienced in this simulation of the real striation frequency represents a much lower variation than the one we observe with different fix dx or with higher values of the factor A , as we can appreciate in both figures 14 and 15.

Figure 17: Deposition profile of electron density distribution over a set of 20 runs of HPI2 in a LFS case, varying A factor to calculate dx from 0.5 to 2 in random uniform distribution. Continuous line is the mean of the electron density distribution and the width of the bands represents two times the standard deviation. Input data from shot 55589 in WEST. This shows the region where the highest variation occurs for the striation frequency randomness.

3.3 Drift stop analysis: rational surfaces

Along the section 3.1 we have seen the deposition profiles for a LFS case, where two peaks can be observed. The reason for these two peaks may be the position of rational surfaces stopping the drift and therefore increasing the deposition around these rational surfaces. These values may correspond to the

integer and half integer values of q (safety factor), where the connection lines discussed that stop the drift are notoriously shorter. So in this section we will perform an analysis in the same LFS case to determine this effect. Note that although the drift of the plasmoid can be stopped, the propagation of the pellet is unaltered, because the pellet doesn't suffer the drift as it is not charged.

The effect of rational surfaces of the q profile (safety factor) in the drift stopping, and therefore in the deposition profile, has been explained in the section 2.3. This effect is going to be checked in the HPI2 model (including the new dx feature). We will shift the safety factor profile to achieve rational surfaces in different radius to test the change in the deposition profile.

In the figure 18(a) we can see the output Δn_e of HPI2 in the studied LFS injection case, along with the q -profile. The intersection of the q -profile with the integer and semi-integer are represented by vertical dashed lines, this would represent the most relevant rational surfaces for drift stopping. We clearly see the correlation between the surroundings of the rational surface $q = 2$ and the first deposition peak, same thing happens with the second peak and $q = 2.5$. The reason why we don't observe this effect for integers or semi-integers higher than 2.5 is because those position are mostly in the edge, where less (or none) plasmoids appears, as the temperature and density is much lower. Also, as we are simulating a LFS injection, the contribution of edge deposited plasmoids is small and the contributions of the the bigger ones, deposited later, will be superimposed on the former (as drift goes towards LFS). This can perturb a possible peak due to external rational surfaces in the edge.

To understand this rational surfaces driven peak deposition, we can infer how, close to the rational surfaces the drift stops and the plasmoids start to accumulate, however when the ablation overcomes this rational surfaces the deposition decays again as the drift appears, if we have enough material to ablate, another peak will appear as we observe in the figure 18(a).

If we move to the figure 18(b), we don't observe two clear peaks anymore, instead we have a clear and big peak close to the position where $q = 2.5$. The only thing that have changed here is a shift on the q -profile, as we see in the figure 19. The reason, again, why we don't have a very clear peak at $q = 3$ is because it is too close to the edge, however is less close than before, so we have a small perturbation around this rational surface. Also, the effect for a rational surface should be higher the lower the q is, because the connection line that make the drift decrease is shorter (so more faster and more effective). The next rational surface after the peak ($q = 2$) is located so deep into the core that the pellet has been mostly ablated so there is not enough plasmoids to feel the drift stopping effect, so we don't observe a peak in this location.

In the last case, showed in the figure 18(c), we have shifted a bit more the safety factor profile. What we can see is two deposition peaks which are not straightforward to differentiate, this is due to how close the two rational surfaces causing them ($q = 2.5$ and $q = 3$) are between each other. Other than that, we still see the same effect: rational surfaces conditioning the position of the ablation peaks and the number of them.

To review in detail the three q -profiles along with the resulting HPI2 deposition profiles we can see the figure 19, where apart from the shift in the q -profile we can observe the change in the magnitude of the peak just changing the q -profile. This is just one of the numerous parameters that can affect the deposition profile in HPI2 model and in the experimentation.

Figure 18: Deposition profile of electron density (blue solid lines), along with the safety factor q (red solid lines) and their rational surfaces of interest (vertical dashed orange lines). Low field side injection case run with HPI2 model unmodified (a), first modification of q -profile (b) and second modification of q -profile (c).

Figure 19: Comparison between three safety factors profiles (red) and the resulting HPI2 deposition profiles (blue).

4 HPI2 Model Validation in WEST Tokamak

After introducing the upgrade to the model, we would like to validate HPI2 with different plasma shots in tokamak WEST where pellet fuelling has been used. Comparing the experimental results with the predictions of the model in the moment of the pellet injection. This would be the first time in which the HPI2 model is validated in the tokamak WEST, on top of that we make this validation effort using our last upgrade of the model regarding the "dx" parameter.

4.1 Validation method

The main output of HPI2 and the most relevant one is the deposition profile, so it would make sense to compare the deposition profile after pellet predicted by HPI2 with the one observed in the experimental case. However, the reconstructed electron density profile of WEST doesn't have the time resolution that we need for the pellet modelling validation (everything happens in 1 ms approximatedly). This, the numerous uncertainties and, occasionally, some problems that diagnostics can face, keep us from using this method.

We haven't used the reflectometer density reconstruction due to the low time resolution and specially because the post pellet n_e profile is likely to be hollow, and the edge reflectometer (the only one available in last WEST campaign) is not able to capture it, so the comparison with the HPI2 model output profile is not simple.

To carry out the validation of the model, the main diagnostic that we have used is the WEST interferometer, the main reasons are the high time resolution and the low uncertainty. Then we would like to introduce this diagnostic a little bit.

In a tokamak, an interferometer is used to measure the line-integrated density of the plasma along different lines of sight. This measurement provides information about the density of the plasma at various locations within the tokamak. The basic principle of an interferometer involves the interference of two or more beams of light. In a tokamak interferometer, a laser beam is typically used as the light source. The laser beam is split into two paths: a reference beam and a probe beam. The reference beam is directed along a known path that does not pass through the plasma. This beam serves as a reference for comparison with the probe beam. The probe beam, on the other hand, passes through the plasma and interacts with the plasma particles. As the probe beam passes through the plasma, it experiences a phase shift due to the refractive index of the plasma, which is related to the density of the plasma. The phase shift of the probe beam is directly proportional to the line-integrated density along its path. After passing through the plasma, the probe beam is recombined with the reference beam. The interference between the two beams creates an interference pattern, which can be observed and analyzed. By measuring the intensity of the interference pattern, it is possible to determine the phase shift of the probe beam caused by the plasma. This phase shift can then be used to calculate the line-integrated density along the path of the probe beam.

Basically, to perform the validation we have compared the line integrated density of the experimental values for each of the Line of Sight (LoS) of the WEST interferometer, with the prediction for HPI2. However, as HPI2 output are plasma profiles (not line integrated densities), to compare both we have used the reconstructed magnetic equilibrium, computed with the NICE code [16], and the predicted deposition profile to reconstruct the prediction of Line of Sight using synthetic diagnostic code Syndi [17]. In this way we can actually compare how the HPI2 model is performing in any shot where interferometer is working.

In the figure 20 we can see the different 10 Lines of Sight that the WEST interferometer uses. While the LoS 3, 5, 7 and 10 goes either throughout or either next to the core, the LoS 1 goes through the X-point, and the LoS 2, 4, 6 and 8 goes through more peripheral regions of the plasma. During this study we

will exclude the LoS 1, 2 and 9, for being too close to the edge, so they are less relevant in terms of core fueling. Also the measures in these lines are more affected by other processes less relevant for the HPI2 model, as edge transport or radiation.

As commented, the high time resolution of the observations is also one of the key reasons we used

Figure 20: Poloidal cut showing the trajectory of the 10 Lines of Sight used in the interferometer of the tokamak WEST. Contour lines show flux surface reconstructed by the NICE code. Red closed line shows the LCFS. Black contour line show the elements closest to the plasma in the tokamak chamber. LoS 3, 5, 7 and 10 (in red) compound the core branch, LoS 4, 6 and 8 (in blue) compound the edge branch, and LoS 1, 2 and 9 (grey) will not be taken into account in this study.

interferometer data to test the model since the entire ablation and homogenization process for one pellet occurs in a 1 ms scale, demanding high time resolution for comparing results.

4.1.1 Uncertainty in validation

To perform this validation effort, we need to be aware of the different uncertainties that can appear. Several factors contribute to these uncertainties, and their effects can be critical in accurately predicting and analyzing experimental results.

One significant challenge arises from the loss of mass during the transportation of pellets through the guide tube. This loss is particularly pronounced during high-field-side injection as the curved guide tube is longer. As the pellets slide along the guide tube, they may experience fragmentation or ablation, leading to a substantial reduction in the total mass available for fueling the plasma. Consequently, the actual amount of fuel delivered to the plasma can differ significantly from the initially launched amount. This mass loss introduces uncertainties in the reconstructed line-integrated density, making it difficult to precisely quantify the plasma's fueling and performance.

Moreover, the uncertainty in the velocity of the injected pellets compounds the issue in a lower scale. The velocity of the pellets can vary due to manufacturing variations, again it can specially decrease in HFS injections, even the pellet could find some dust in the way to the tokamak chamber. Since the fueling efficiency is closely related to the pellet velocity, inaccuracies in its determination can further contribute to uncertainties in the line-integrated density reconstruction.

Another critical aspect influencing reconstruction uncertainty lies in the profiles of electron temperature (T_e) and electron density (n_e) before pellet injection. The pre-injection plasma profiles serve as input for HPI2, so any uncertainties in these profiles can significantly affect the final predictions obtained from the model. In the case of n_e different inversion methods, coming from the same interferometer and reflectometer data, can result in different electron density profiles. As a result, variations in T_e and n_e can change the plasma that the pellet is facing, so the ablation and the final profiles. This drawback could be avoided with a more precise profile reconstruction, as it happens with Thomson Scattering diagnostic, unfortunately this diagnostic is not available in WEST tokamak yet, but is planned to be incorporated in the future.

Additionally, there is some time uncertainty, as the only time we have for the pellet injection is the time when the command is sent to the injector, but not when the pellet enters the LCFS. Moreover, there is a sensible variation between the time it takes to arrive to the LCFS in HFS injection (take longer) and the time it takes for the LFS injection. This has to be carefully taken into account when comparing the results.

Finally, as we saw in the section 3.2, the difference on striation frequency, or the difference in the position where the different plasmoids are ejected in relation with the position of the rational surfaces of the safety factor can affect the final density profile almost a $\pm 5\%$.

In conclusion, uncertainties in the line-integrated density reconstruction in tokamaks after pellet injection arise from the loss of pellet mass in the guide tube, variations in pellet velocity, and uncertainties in pre-injection plasma profiles and injection time. To cope with these uncertainties and carry out the validation effort, we will perform scans over pellet size or pellet velocity in the different shots. This is also due to the fact that the diagnostic that measured the real velocity and the real mass of the pellet has not been working at least in the last campaign of WEST, so we are forced to estimate it from the pellet injector configuration. Also, observing through interferometry the change in total number of electrons inside the plasma just after the injection serves to approximate the real mass of the pellet entering the separatrix. Looking at the accuracy of the model with this calculated pellet mass will show us the model performance in WEST tokamak.

4.2 Results

To validate the HPI2 model in the tokamak WEST, we have developed the tools mentioned above regarding the Line of Sight comparisons. In this section we will show them to effectively confirm the validation of the model with the experimental data.

4.2.1 One plasma

We have started doing a deeper study in one pellet injection in the HFS pellet injection shot 58656 from the campaign C7 of WEST. The election of this shot seemed adequate as it is an ohmic shot (not additional heating, i.e. no fast particles that can complicate the ablation process), so the HPI2 model could have less trouble to match the experiment, also it is a shot from the last campaign so we have first hand information about it, and we are particularly interested in HFS injection shots as it would be the most likely fuelling method in the future machines. Among the 3 pellets that are injected in this shot we choose (arbitrarily) to show in a detailed way the HPI2 results for the first one. In this section we will focus in the results and diagnostics that are going to allow us to validate the model. In the figure 21 we can see the ablation path (so the trajectory) of the pellets injected in the WEST shot 58656 through the High Field Side, from the upper side.

To illustrate the method of comparison we have the figure 22 where we can see the effect of the pellet injection in the line integrated density measured by the Line of Sight 8 of the interferometer. We appreciate this steep increase in n_l due to the effect of ablation and homogenization of the pellet that happens in

Figure 21: HPI2 output showing the trajectory and ablation of the first pellet injected in the WEST shot 58656 using a poloidal cut. Contour lines show the magnetic equilibrium just after the pellet injection. Red closed line show the LCFS. Black contour show the elements closest to the plasma in the tokamak chamber.

less than 1 ms. In this figure we can also see the prediction for this line integrated density in HPI2, the prediction as commented, comes from the predicted deposition profile by HPI2. So this predictions correspond to the value that n_l should take when the density stabilizes just after the pellet injection. That's why we compare this prediction with the interferometer value a bit before the peak. We see that although the fit is not perfect, we can infer a close result, however for different LoS that cover different regions of the plasma (see figure 20), we can have different levels of accuracy. To perform the validation we have chosen the LoS 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10 which correspond to region not too peripheric that can be governed by effects not represented in HPI2.

However, as commented in the section 4.1.1, the uncertainties in the data can make difficult to compare the results. We will follow with the analysis of different sources of uncertainty and their effect on the final result.

- Pellet Mass analysis.** The biggest uncertainty in the case of the HFS injection come from the mass and velocity of the pellet, but the effect of the mass is prominent compared with the velocity. For this reason we decided to perform an analysis in the pellet mass that effectively enters in the separatrix. This is exactly what we can find in the figure 23, where α stands for the ratio between HPI2 n_l prediction and reconstructed n_l by interferometry measurement $\alpha = \frac{n_{l,HPI2}}{n_{l,Interferometry}}$. We see for the different LoS a linear decrease in the HPI2 prediction when decreasing the injected mass. This seems to make sense, the lower the mass injected the lower the density, so lower line integrated density (n_l). We clearly distinguish two branches, in LoS 3, 5, 7 and 10 (which correspond to regions next to the core, so core branch) HPI2 over-predicts n_l much more than LoS 4, 6 and 8 (which correspond to regions closer to the edge, so edge branch). This fact tells us that HPI2 is predicting much higher pellet deposition in the core than the reality, however as we decrease the mass, the values in the core decrease faster than the others, probably because lower mass means lower pellet penetration (lower deposition in the core). We can observe how, around 30 % of the

Figure 22: Black line is the interferometer data for LoS 8 during the first pellet of WEST shot 58656. In the plot we can also appreciate the launching time, the HPI2 prediction and the comparison time for the interferometers with the markers showed in the legend.

total mass, the accuracy of all the LoS comes closer and the HPI2 model overpredict between 15 % and 0 % for the LoS going through the core region, and it is set between 5 % up and 10 % down of the full accuracy for the rest of LoS. Indeed, this represents a reasonable accuracy for HPI2. We can have the intuition that the real mass value can be close to this area, so we check it taking into account the change in the number of electrons in the whole plasma and the pellet density. The difference in electrons was around $14 \cdot 10^{19}$ electrons, estimated by interferometry, we can appreciate it in the figure 32 in the Appendix A. Therefore, we estimate the real mass to be around 38 % of the theoretical mass, which tells us that the HPI2 model is performing adequately well if we look at the figure 23.

- **Initial Velocity analysis.** Regarding the effect on the uncertainty in the velocity, as we have anticipated from the NGS scaling, it is much lower than the effect of the pellet mass, but still we have run the HPI2 model several times to test it. The results, in a similar way to the last figure, can be seen in the figure 24. We see the same two branches in this case, the LoS that goes through the core and the LoS that doesn't. In the former, the HPI2 prediction slightly decrease when velocity is lower, as penetration will necessarily be lower, so is not reaching the core that much. However in the latter, the prediction grows with less velocity as the deposition will be placed closer to the edge regions. Both branches tend to converge. Also note that the results of the figure comes from model runs taking into account 75 % of the mass, which is not the optimum value but serve to show the effect.
- **T_e profile analysis.** The electron temperature profile is a factor that also can affect the results in HPI2, as the ablation will depend in the temperature, and HPI2 will not calculate the plasmoids until the temperature is high enough, so this can specially affect the pellet penetration. To perform this analysis we have used, apart from the T_e profile that comes from ECE diagnostics, we have also used the upper and lower bound in the uncertainty of this measure. We can see those three profiles in the figure 25(a) and appreciate the magnitude of the expected uncertainty of the T_e reconstruction. So running HPI2 and comparing with the experimental data from the interferometer, we obtain the results in figure 25(b). We have used a 38 % of the mass and the 100 % of the velocity. We see

Figure 23: Accuracy (in terms of line integrated density, n_l) of the HPI2 model for first pellet in 58656 shot with respect to the pellet mass chosen to run the model. α represents the ratio between HPI2 prediction and reconstructed n_l by interferometry. Different colors represent the results in the different branches of Lines of Sight of the interferometer. Horizontal line at 1 represents full accuracy of HPI2 with respect to the interferometer.

Figure 24: Accuracy (in terms of line integrated density, n_l) of the HPI2 model for first pellet in 58656 shot with respect to the initial pellet velocity chosen to run the model. The HPI2 mass was set as 75 % of the pellet mass. α represents the ratio between HPI2 prediction and reconstructed n_l by interferometry. Different colors represent the results in the different branches of Lines of Sight of the interferometer. Horizontal line at 1 represents full accuracy of HPI2 with respect to the interferometer..

higher accuracy for the upper bound, so higher temperature than the one measured. In this case as we increase the temperature we get the n_l of the LoS going through the core to decrease, because as we increase temperature we decrease penetration, so less deposition will get to the core. As more deposition will stay near to the edge, the other LoS predictions increase. Due to this in the lower bound all the accuracy values are closer to 1 and closer between each other. It is worth noting that the pellet mass used, unlike the velocity analysis, has been 38 % and the initial velocity 100 %, both respect to the theoretical values.

We can infer that, even though the effect is less pronounced for the T_e profile than for the pellet mass, the uncertainty in T_e profile is a crucial factor in the accuracy of HPI2.

(a)

(b)

Figure 25: T_e profile before first pellet injection in 58656 WEST shot with upper and lower bounds of ECE reconstruction uncertainty (a), and HPI2 accuracy compared against interferometry LoS reconstruction using T_e profile, upper and lower band (b).

While we could find the optimum values using velocity and mass (something like 40 % of the mass and 40 % of the velocity for example), we may have the risk of overfitting these two parameters to achieve the desired result, instead of what we really want, which is validate the results against the experiment. So we prefer to only take into account the most impactful parameter while acknowledging that there could be another source of uncertainties that can make our prediction to experiment some variation. On top of that we can estimate the mass of the pellet using the total number of electrons, but we don't have anything like this for the velocity. Then this validation is mainly based on the results that are obtained around the expected pellet mass area.

4.2.2 Multiple cases

So far, the results for the first pellet of the shot 58656 has been presented to deeply illustrate the validation exercise, then in this section we will show the pellet mass analysis for different pellets in both the HFS injection shot 58656 and the LFS injection shot 55589 (from campaign C4). Other 2 shots were performed in the last C7 campaign using HFS pellet injection, shot 58657 and 58658. However, in the former pellets seem to have a very low impact which implies that the shot was not fully satisfying in terms of pellet fuelling, in the latter the pellets were directed towards the X-point and an imprecision in the equilibrium reconstruction has not allowed HPI2 to model the injection as it doesn't perceive the pellet entering in the LCFS. In conclusion, to finish the validation we will make use of the 2 pellets left to analyse in 58656 (HFS) and the 5 pellets injected in 55589 (LFS).

We will start with the results corresponding to the HFS injection shot. Therefore in the figure 26 we can see the pellet mass analysis in the accuracy of HPI2 for the second pellet, in the same manner as the figure 23. Again, the estimated mass correspond to 38 % to the theoretical mass (as the estimation has been performed for all the injections in the shot), and around this region we can find for the core LoS branch between 10 % and 5 % of overprediction and for the edge LoS branch between 0 % and 10 % of underprediction in n_l , this indeed indicates the good precision of HPI2 in the pellet injection. The analogies with the figure 23 corresponding to the first pellet are evident: same linear tendency, close values and two branches of LoS (core and edge branches).

The results for third and last pellet injection can be found in the figure 27, where we also can see a good match around 38 % of the total mass, however the precision is around 5 % lower in the core branch with respect to the other injections and the two branches of LoS are more differentiated. Nevertheless the same behavior as the other two injections can be observed. With this we can conclude that in this HFS pellet injection shot the match of HPI2 predictions with the interferometer data is good considering the pellet mass that we expect to enter in the LCFS.

After analysing the results for the HFS injection, we move to the LFS injection in the WEST shot 55589. 5 pellets were injected in this shot, all of them from the LFS. In analogy with the last shot, we have run the HPI2 predictions and performed a pellet mass analysis on them. As before, we have also calculated the expected mass to enter in the LCFS using the electron perturbation for this shot.

In the figures 28, 29 and 30 we can observe the mass scan in the accuracy of HPI2 for the 5 pellets, in analogy with the previous graphs. We can see how in all of them we invert what we used to have in the last shot, now the HPI2 predictions of the LoS edge branch are the ones over-predicting, and the core branch are closer to under-predict n_l . This could mean that unlike the HFS injection case, the real penetration towards the core is a bit deeper than what the HPI2 model predicts. On the other hand, we conserve the same lineal behavior with the mass, however the two branch are not so well differentiated in most of the pellets. The estimated mass with the consideration of the number of electrons entering in the LCFS is 75 %, although this value is approximate as the fuelling efficiency is lower in LFS injection because of the ∇B drift direction (pushing some matter out of the LCFS). However, this pellet mass is

Figure 26: Accuracy (in terms of line integrated density, n_l) of the HPI2 model for the second pellet in 58656 shot with respect to the pellet mass chosen to run the model. α represents the ratio between HPI2 prediction and reconstructed n_l by interferometry. Different colors represent the results in the different branches of Lines of Sight of the interferometer. Horizontal line at 1 represents full accuracy of HPI2 with respect to the interferometer.

higher than in the HFS case, clearly because of the lack of curved and long pipes to inject the pellet, where we lose most of our mass and velocity. We should also consider the important fact that in HFS injection the ∇B drift goes in favour of the pellet injection, so the deposition happens deeper than the ablation, however in the LFS case this drift goes in opposite direction, so the deposition happens usually farther from the core. This fact could be an important factor to determine why the LoS going through the edge, specially the LoS 4 and 6 (refer to figure 20), have lower performance (reaching 30 % over-prediction) compared with the rest of LoS comparisons. As stated, this means that the penetration until the core is higher than the one expected by HPI2 predictions. However, for the desired mass of 75 %, in the rest of LoS we find a good agreement, between 10 % over and 10 % under the full accuracy. Although in the pellet 1 and 3 it can be worse in the LoS close to the core and reach 20 % of under-prediction.

Finally, the agreement in this LFS injection case seems reasonably good for the targeted mass region, excepting the 2 LoS more peripheric (4 and 6), in which we may find some excessively high over-prediction. However, further studies in velocity or temperature or density profile could refine this result.

4.3 Discussion

All along this section we have introduced the validation method, the possible uncertainties, and finally, showed the results in 2 WEST shots with pellet injection, one from the HFS and the other from the LFS. Observing the different results for the different Lines of Sight, we have been able to infer which region are predicted better and how. Overall, in HFS injection, we can say that the LoS close to the core tend to overpredict the line integrated density n_l while the LoS close to the edge tend to underpredict it, the opposite thing happens in LFS injection, which is an indicator about the drift direction role. However, the margins of this error are close enough to consider them into a reasonable frame in which the uncertainties due to velocity, n_e and T_e profiles can be responsible. We see this in the difference in the accuracy for different pellets in the same shot.

It is worth noting that although we have decided not to go too deep in the velocity scan to avoid over-fitting the results, the effect we observed in the first pellet of the HFS shot tells us that the difference

Figure 27: Accuracy (in terms of line integrated density, n_l) of the HPI2 model for the third pellet in 58656 shot with respect to the pellet mass chosen to run the model. α represents the ratio between HPI2 prediction and reconstructed n_l by interferometry. Different colors represent the results in the different branches of Lines of Sight of the interferometer. Horizontal line at 1 represents full accuracy of HPI2 with respect to the interferometer.

(a) Pellet 1

Figure 28: This graph represents the accuracy in n_l of the HPI2 model for the first pellet injected in the 55589 shot with respect to the pellet mass chosen to run the model. α represents the ratio between HPI2 prediction and reconstructed n_l by interferometry. Different colors represent the results in the different branches of Lines of Sight of the interferometer. Horizontal line at 1 represents full accuracy of HPI2 with respect to the interferometer.

between the LoS could be minimised in an optimal velocity for the HFS shot, so the penetration would be smaller and we will not both over-predict and under-predict that much.

We have estimated the appropriate mass for the HFS and LFS injection shots. It is something expected that the estimated mass loss in the guide tubes is much higher in the HFS than the LFS case, also

(a) Pellet 2

(b) Pellet 3

Figure 29: These graphs represent the accuracy in n_i of the HPI2 model for the second and third pellets in the 55589 shot with respect to the pellet mass chosen to run the model. α represents the ratio between HPI2 prediction and reconstructed n_i by interferometry. Different colors represent the results in the different branches of Lines of Sight of the interferometer. Horizontal line at 1 represents full accuracy of HPI2 with respect to the interferometer.

we expect a bigger decrease in velocity too. But due to the lack of diagnostics, this quantities will stay as mere estimations for the moment.

The scope of this part of the study was to validate the HPI2 code, including the new update regarding the spacial step for ablation. Then, after examining these two shots from WEST tokamak, we can infer that the accuracy of the HPI2 model, taking into account the uncertainties involved, fulfills the requirements of a predicting model for the pellet injection in the tokamak WEST.

An important point to note is that the upcoming experimental campaigns in the tokamak WEST will

(a) Pellet 4

(b) Pellet 5

Figure 30: These graphs represent the accuracy (in terms of line integrated density, n_l) of the HPI2 model for the fourth and fifth pellets in the 55589 shot with respect to the pellet mass chosen to run the model. α represents the ratio between HPI2 prediction and reconstructed n_l by interferometry. Different colors represent the results in the different branches of Lines of Sight of the interferometer. Horizontal line at 1 represents full accuracy of HPI2 with respect to the interferometer.

soon feature the incorporation of lacking diagnostics for the n_e profile (measured through Thomson scattering) and pellet parameters such as mass, velocity, and timing. Also It is worth noting that the interest of the fusion community lies specially in the HFS injection, as tokamaks in the future will probably rely on it as the main fuelling system, so the good results in the HFS case represents good news for the HPI2 model and its future utilization.

5 Conclusion and Future Outlook

All along this research effort, the main scope has been improving the HPI2 model and validate it in WEST tokamak.

The first point has been addressed through the replacement of the fix and arbitrary parameter dx , with a new dx which is purely dependant in the exit time of the pellet from the plasmoid and in the pellet velocity. This approach is much more physical and the results described in the section 3 show a robust agreement with the most precise results using the old dx parameter. The creation of this new parameter has allowed us to improve the computation time when compared with the most precise runs of HPI2, while improving the precision too. On top of that we have defined a new factor "A" that can decrease the computation time and not loose too much accuracy when lower than 2. This factor has allowed us also to simulate with HPI2 the effect that the variation in the striation frequency can have in the deposition profile.

Apart from this, a study in the peak deposition depending on the safety factor profile and rational surfaces has been performed using HPI2, finally results agree in the dependence in this model of rational surfaces with the position of peaks of deposition.

The validation effort has been addressed comparing the deposition results from HPI2 with two experimental shots from WEST tokamak, one of them using HFS injection and the other LFS injection. As the diagnostics and their precision haven't allowed to compare directly the HPI2 output profiles with the experimental profiles after the pellet, we have used the line integrated density coming from 7 Lines of Sight. We have calculated the line integrated density predictions for HPI2 and we have compared them with the experimental measurements. The main uncertainty has been the mass of the pellet, due to the erosion in guide tubes (specially in HFS injection) and the own mass precision of the injector. To avoid this issue, we have estimated the mass of the pellet that enters the separatrix with the total number of electrons (calculated by interferometry), and we have done a mass scan running HPI2 several times. Finally we have shown the results in terms of accuracy for different pellet mass. Good agreement around the desired mass has been shown, specially in the HFS case. In the LFS case, the HPI2 prediction for the most peripheral Lines of Sight had more trouble to match the experiment. However, other sources of uncertainty as T_e and n_e before pellet profiles or pellet velocity, have been left apart somehow for not being as relevant as the pellet mass.

The validation of the HPI2 model has offered reasonably good results that make us believe that this pellet deposition model is fully functional in WEST tokamak.

Next steps could be directed towards a more intensive check in the other sources of uncertainty, or using more precise diagnostics that could exist in WEST in the future, such as Thomson scattering diagnostic.

It seems meaningful to mention that, after this master internship, I will continue working in the pellet modelling in HPI2 developing reduced models for integrated modelling of the tokamak, as part of my PhD thesis. This time it won't happen at the IRFM, I will continue in the Dutch Institute for Fundamental Energy Research (DIFFER).

Finally, a notable achievement stemming from this internship is the successful transfer of pellet injection physics expertise from Bernard Pégourié to myself, setting the stage for my upcoming PhD endeavors. This exchange gains additional significance considering Bernard's imminent retirement and the limited pool of specialists in this domain within the fusion community. The acquired knowledge not only empowers my academic journey but also underscores the collaborative spirit and the continuity of research excellence within the field.

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A Appendix: Additional figures

Here some relevant figures will be included to add clarity to the explanations, although they are not essential for it.

Figure 31: Illustrative representation of the ejection of the plasmoid (light brown), when the pellet (dark blue) and its neutral cloud (green), and the posterior plasmoid formation, completing the cyclic process. The time t_{exit} represents the amount of time that this ejection takes.

Figure 32: Estimated number of electrons inside the last closed flux surface (red line) and sum of line integrated density using interferometry (blue line) in function of time. Pellet injection is indicated with a red circle. Data for WEST shot 58656 using pellet injection.